

NEOLOGISM IN ENGLISH, UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES INTRODUCED BY COVID - 19

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ABSTRACT

Languages have always been adaptable for different periods. One interesting thing about languages is that they never stop evolving except the ones out of use. Languages gain from whatever positive or negative happens during a specific period. The pandemic of Covid – 19 has expanded all languages with new vocabulary, phrases and expressions and the following article will focus on the ones in Uzbek, English and Russian languages.

INTRODUCTION

Globalisation and introduction of neologisms have expanded in recent years as technology has developed more rapidly than ever. People communicate and sometimes create new words or phrases which can easily spread all over the world and become popular thanks to the internet and mass media.

DISCUSSION

In 2020, the effects of the pandemic on society and language were clear to see in Uzbekistan as well as all over the world.

First of all, we need to define the meaning of the term “neologism”. In the Longman dictionary of Contemporary English, it is

explained as “a new word or expression, or a word used with a new meaning” whilst Wikipedia defines the term as “a relatively recent or isolated word is in the process of entering common use, but has not yet been fully accepted into mainstream language”. From the two definitions, it can be stated that “neologism” means a new word or phrase introduced by the interconnection of two or more languages.

The outbreak of Covid – 19 has resulted in many words being used alongside less common words which spread as fast as the virus. Some existing words have started to be used and have become common in many parts of the world. Here are some examples in English, Uzbek and Russian languages

English	Uzbek	Russian
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Corona virus	Koronavirus	Каронавирус
Quarantine	Karantin	Карантин
Case fatality	O'lim xolati/ko'rsatkichi	Показатели смертности
Epidemic	Epidemiya	Эпидемия
Pandemic	Pandemiya	Пандемия
Epicenter	Epitsentr	Эпицентр
Face covering	Maska taqish	Покрывать лицо
Face mask	Maska	Маски для лица
Infected	Kasallangan	Зараженные
Lockdown	Lokdaun (karantin)	Локдаун (карантин)
Personal protective equipment	Shaxsiy ximoya vositasi	Средства индивидуальной защиты
Social distance	Ijtimoiy masofa	Социальная дистанция
Self-isolation	O'zini yakkalash	Сама изоляция
Vaccine	Vaksina	Вакцина
Remote education	Masofaviy ta'lim	Удаленька, дистанционка

Except the existing words that became common, some new words were coined which quickly became popular. For instance: **Coronaskeptics** are those who think that corona virus does not exist, **Coronaenthusiastics** are vice versa, **Coronapanic** is the panic or rumors about

the virus among people, **Covidiots** are people who consciously disobey the rules of quarantine, **Coronafakes** are fake news about corona virus and lockdown.

Regardless of the fact that the pandemic brought nearly the same terms in all languages, some languages gained phrases according to cultural and social factors of

the society. For example, the virus established the words like **Karantikul** or **Worcation**, that appeared in Uzbek language after the whole Uzbekistan was quarantined in March, which resulted in giving an unplanned vocation to schoolchildren and students. The affix **-kul** was taken from the word **kanikul** which means vocation. During the quarantine many people were jobless and lack of money. In order to support needy families, most volunteers rose charities, restaurants delivered free meals to doctors which in Russian was called as **Ковидарность**, similar to the word **Солидарность**, unity. As self-isolating was established as one of the main rules of the quarantine, conferences, meetings and lessons had to be conducted on the Zoom platform which led to the introduction of an Uzbek neologism **Zoomlanish**, meaning online work.

Professor of the department of journalism and med communication at

North-West Academy of Public Administration Olesya Glushenka states that nearly 50 neologisms have been brought into the Russian language by covid – 19 and some exiting words developed another meaning. For example, the basic meaning of the Russian word **корона** means royal crown symbolizing the governmental power of monarchy, but these days rarely does anybody use it in the original meaning as it now means the virus or the word **коронованный** is not used to direct at a crowned person, but at an infected person.

CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The recent circumstances and the facts that have been listed above prove the fact that languages are flexible again. Whatever happening in the world enriches the history and the language.

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